

1 Running Head: Ruminant fermentation of forage brassicas

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3 Enteric methane production and ruminal fermentation of forage brassica diets fed in continuous
4 culture

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24 **ABSTRACT**

25 The aim of the current study was to determine nutrient digestibility, VFA production, N
26 metabolism, and CH₄ production of canola (*Brassica napus* L.), rapeseed (*B. napus* L.), turnip
27 (*B. rapa* L.), and annual ryegrass (*Lolium multiflorum* Lam.) fed with orchardgrass (*Dactylis*
28 *glomerata* L.) in continuous culture. Diets were randomly assigned to fermentors in a 4 × 4 Latin
29 square design using 7 d for adaptation and 3 d for collection. Diets were: 1) 50% orchardgrass +
30 50% annual ryegrass (ARG); 2) 50% orchardgrass + 50% canola (CAN); 3) 50% orchardgrass +
31 50% rapeseed (RAP); and 4) 50% orchardgrass + 50% turnip (TUR). Feedings (82 g DM/d)
32 occurred 4 times daily throughout 4, 10-d periods at 730, 1030, 1400, and 1900 h. Methane
33 samples were collected every 10 min using a photoacoustic gas analyzer (LumaSense
34 Technologies, Inc.; Santa Clara, CA) during the last 3 d of the experiment. Effluent samples
35 were collected on d 8, 9, and 10, composited by fermentor, and analyzed for VFA and pH as well
36 as DM, OM, CP, and fiber fractions for determination of nutrient digestibility. Forage samples
37 were analyzed for CP, NDF, ADF, minerals, and glucosinolate (GLS) concentrations. Data were
38 analyzed using the GLIMMIX procedure of SAS. Apparent DM, OM, and NDF digestibilities
39 and true DM and OM digestibilities were similar ($P > 0.28$) among diets (45.1, 63.2, 44.1, 67.1,
40 and 87.2%, respectively). Total VFA (87.2 mol/100 mol), pH (6.47) and acetate (A: 44.6
41 mol/100 mol) were also not different ($P > 0.20$) among diets. The A:P (P = propionate) ratio was
42 greater ($P < 0.01$) in ARG and CAN than RAP and TUR. Daily CH₄ production was greater ($P <$
43 0.01) in ARG than all other diets (68.9 vs. 11.2 mg/d). Methane, whether expressed as g per g of
44 OM, NDF, digestible OM, or digestible NDF fed was greatest ($P < 0.01$) in ARG but similar (P
45 > 0.18) among brassica diets. A significant negative correlation was observed between total GLS
46 and CH₄ production. However, when multiple regression analysis on CH₄ production was

47 completed, neither total GLS nor individual GLS were a significant component of the model.
48 Addition of brassicas provided similar nutrient digestibility to ARG while reducing daily CH₄
49 production, potentially making brassicas an alternative for ARG in pasture-based ruminant diets.

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51 **KEYWORDS:** brassica, continuous culture, methane, ruminal fermentation

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INTRODUCTION

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Forage brassicas are cool-season annual forages that can be used for grazing during the summer in the Mid-Atlantic and Northeast US and late fall throughout the temperate zone when cool-season perennial pastures may not be as productive (Hall and Jung, 2008). Many brassica varieties exist, including vegetable, oilseed, and forage varieties; however, forage varieties have been bred to mature more quickly and produce greater above-ground biomass than their vegetable and oilseed counterparts. Brassica species include rapeseed (*Brassica napus* L.), turnip (*B. rapa* L.), kale (*B. oleracea* L.), radish (*Raphanus sativus* L.), and swede (*B. napobrassica* (L.) Mill). Forage variety trials throughout the eastern United States have shown the high biomass potential of forage brassicas (1500 – 5000 kg DM/ha; Darby et al., 2013, 2015; Simon et al., 2014). Further studies reported high CP concentrations (>20%), low NDF (20-35%) and high DM digestibility (>85%; Darby et al., 2013; Villalobos and Brummer, 2015). The combination of greater biomass during periods of perennial forage shortages and greater forage nutritive value has increased producer interest in using brassicas for pasture-based ruminants with high nutrient requirements (i.e., beef stockers, finishing lambs, and lactating dairy cows).

Brassicas contain a class of sulfur-containing plant secondary metabolites called glucosinolates (GLS). The type and quantity of GLS in each brassica varies with cultivar, agronomic management, and climatic conditions (Gustine and Jung, 1985; Tripathi and Mishra, 2007). Ingestion of substantial amounts of GLS can have adverse effects on animal performance and health. These include reduced DMI, ADG, I and Cu deficiencies, and kale anemia (Gustine and Jung, 1985). For this reason, nutritionists typically suggest limiting brassicas to $\leq 50\%$ of daily DMI (Hall and Jung, 2008).

75 Multiple studies (Brask et al., 2013a, 2013b; Storlien et al., 2017) have shown that
76 feeding a diet of 10 – 49% whole rapeseed or rapeseed meal reduces enteric methane emissions
77 in cattle by 9 – 23%. Additionally, Storlien et al. (2017) determined that rapeseed concentrate
78 was still effective at reducing enteric CH₄ 39 d after the initial addition of brassicas into the diet,
79 suggesting that brassicas have the potential for long-term CH₄ reduction. However, to date only a
80 few studies (Sun et al., 2012, 2015; Williams et al., 2016) have reported CH₄ emissions from
81 ruminants consuming forage brassicas. Animals used in these studies were consuming diets that
82 were either 100% forage brassica (Sun et al., 2012, 2015) or that were a brassica/legume mixture
83 (Williams et al., 2016). Furthermore, these studies have been unable to report a causal
84 relationship between individual and total GLS concentration and reduced CH₄ emissions.
85 However, research has shown that the GLS concentration of feeds [i.e., rapeseed and canola (*B.*
86 *napus* L.) meals] is largely responsible for the reduction in CH₄ emissions in ruminants
87 supplemented with these by-products (Busquet et al., 2005; Patra et al., 2010; Storlien et al.,
88 2017). While Sun et al. (2012, 2015) did attempt to determine the relationship between GLS in
89 forage brassicas and reduced enteric CH₄ emissions in lambs, they were unable to prove a causal
90 relationship. Furthermore, no studies have reported CH₄ emissions or rumen fermentation
91 parameters in ruminant systems when a brassica/grass diet has been fed and attempted to
92 establish a causal relationship between total and individual GLS and enteric CH₄ production in
93 brassica/grass mixtures. The objectives of the current study were to 1) determine the effects of 3
94 forage brassicas fed in a 50:50 with orchardgrass on ruminal fermentation, N metabolism, and
95 enteric CH₄ production in continuous culture; and 2) determine if a causal link exists between
96 total GLS concentration and CH₄ production. We hypothesized that feeding forage brassicas in a
97 50:50 mixture with orchardgrass would decrease enteric methane production, while not altering

98 rumen fermentation parameters compared to an annual ryegrass (*Lolium multiflorum*
99 Lam.)/orchardgrass mixture and that multiple regression analysis will reveal a causal relationship
100 between total GLS concentration and CH₄ production.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

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Site, Experimental Design, and Diets

104 On August 26, 2015, ‘KB Supreme’ annual ryegrass (King’s Agriseed, Inc., Ronks, PA),
105 ‘Inspiration’ canola (Rubisco Seed, LLC., Philpot, KY), ‘Barisca’ rapeseed (King’s Agriseed,
106 Inc.), and ‘Appin’ turnip (King’s Agriseed, Inc.) were planted at the Pennsylvania State
107 University Russell E. Larson Agricultural Research Center in Rock Springs, PA. Seeds were
108 drilled into a prepared seedbed using a no-till drill (HEGE 1000; Wintersteiger AG, Waldenburg,
109 Germany). Forage was harvested on November 3, 2015, when forage was ready for grazing
110 (approximately 70d after planting; Hall and Jung, 2008). Orchardgrass (*Dactylis glomerata* L.)
111 was harvested from a 3-yr-old pure stand on April 27, 2016. Orchardgrass was harvested in a
112 vegetative stage of growth, typical of high-quality pastures used for grazing in temperate regions
113 of the United States (25 to 30 cm tall; Dillard et al., 2017). A plot harvester (HEGE 212;
114 Wintersteiger AG; 1.5-m-wide swath), set to a 10-cm stubble height was used to harvest all
115 forage. Within 30 min of harvest, forage was placed in cloth bags and frozen (-4°C) until being
116 freeze-dried (Ultra 35 Super ES; Virtis Co. Inc., Gardiner, NY). Freeze-dried forage was ground
117 to pass through a 1-mm sieve (Wiley mill; Thomson Scientific Inc., Philadelphia, PA). Freeze-
118 dried forages are not nutritionally identical to fresh forages; however, in order to be preserved
119 and ground for use in the experiment, drying was necessary (Soder et al., 2016), and Jones and

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121 Bailey (1972) reported that oven-drying forages could denature protein in plant material and
122 decrease digestibility.

123 The continuous culture fermentor study was conducted at the USDA-Agricultural
124 Research Service, Pasture Systems and Watershed Management Research Unit (University Park,
125 PA) from May to July 2016. Total DM fed to all fermentors was kept constant at 82 g/d for the
126 duration of the experiment. Diets were as follows: (1) 50% orchardgrass + 50% annual ryegrass
127 (ARG); (2) 50% orchardgrass + 50% canola (CAN); (3) 50% orchardgrass + 50% rapeseed
128 (RAP); and (4) 50% orchardgrass + 50% turnip (TUR). Fermentors were fed forage 4 times daily
129 (0730, 1030, 1400, and 1900 h) in equal proportions of the diet. Representative samples of
130 freeze-dried forage were collected from each diet at the beginning of the study and analyzed for
131 nutrient concentrations at a commercial laboratory (Dairy One Laboratories, Ithaca, NY; Table
132 1).

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134 *Continuous Culture System and Operation*

135 The experiment was designed as a 4 × 4 Latin square. Diets were fermented in a 4-unit,
136 continuous culture fermentor system (Applikon Biotechnology, B.V., Schiedam, The
137 Netherlands). Fermentors were fed equal portions of herbage 4 times daily (0730, 1030, 1400,
138 and 1900 h). Solid mean retention time and liquid dilution rate of the fermentors were adjusted
139 daily to 24 h and 10%/h, respectively, and were achieved by regulation of buffer input and
140 effluent volume removal (Bargo et al., 2003; Rico et al., 2012; Soder et al., 2016). Mineral buffer
141 was prepared using the method of Hoover et al. (1976), except that urea was added at a rate of
142 0.4 g/L to simulate recycled N (Weller and Pilgrim, 1974). To achieve the desired retention and
143 dilution rates, the buffer pump was adjusted to 20.6 ± 0.2 mL buffer per 7.5 min. The buffer

144 pumps were on (pulsing) for approximately 4.6 min, at which point they automatically stopped
145 pulsing and did not deliver any buffer into the vessel for the remaining 2.9 min of the 7.5 min
146 cycle. Adjustments to the pulse time were made daily to ensure that 20.6 mL of buffer were
147 delivered every cycle. The daily estimated effluent volume was determined by the daily buffer
148 and feed volume. The effluent pump was set to run for 6 s every 7.5 min and daily effluent
149 volume was adjusted by altering the pump speed. The total volume of effluent that must be
150 removed from the system was calculated using the following equation: $V_{Fluid} = F_{LD} \times V_{Ferm} \times t_r$
151 where V_{Fluid} = total volume of fluid removed for given retention time (mL), F_{LD} = liquid dilution
152 factor (%), V_{Ferm} = volume of the fermenter (mL), and t_r = retention time (hr). The resulting
153 volume is equivalent to the daily effluent fluid volume needed to maintain proper turnover in the
154 system. In order to determine the total effluent volume, the fluid volume needed to be adjusted
155 for the solids (feed) entering the system. Therefore, total volume removed per day is calculated
156 as: $V_{Total} = V_{Fluid} + V_{Solids}$ where V_{Total} = total volume of effluent removed daily (mL) and V_{Solids}
157 = total volume of feed added to the system per day (mL). The amount of effluent to be removed
158 per sample can be determined using $V_{Sample} = V_{Total} / n_s$ where V_{Sample} = volume of effluent to be
159 removed per sample (mL) and n_s = number of samples per day. The chosen number of daily
160 samples for this set-up was 192 samples per day, correlating to a 7 minute and 30 second cycle
161 running continuously for 24 h.

162 A ruminally fistulated, non-pregnant, non-lactating Holstein cow (BW = 794 kg) was
163 used for ruminal fluid and digesta collections in accordance with the Pennsylvania State
164 University Animal Care and Use guidelines (IACUC #46212). The donor cow was group housed
165 and fed a diet of mixed grass hay and grain (75:25 forage-to-concentrate ratio) in a feed bunk for
166 a total of 13.8 kg DM of available feed per cow per day at the Pennsylvania State University

167 Dairy Research Farm (University Park, PA). A vitamin-mineral premix was fed at 1.8% of total
168 DMI in order to meet NRC (2001) recommendations. Approximately 3 h after feeding, 7 L of
169 ruminal fluid was collected with a hand pump into a prewarmed container and maintained at
170 39°C. Hand-grab samples of solid digesta were taken from the ventral, central, and dorsal areas
171 of the rumen. Liquid and solid digesta samples were transported to the laboratory in separate
172 containers. Within 15 min of collection, fluid was strained through 4 layers of cheesecloth and
173 1.5 L poured into each prewarmed, fermentation vat. Each fermentor vat was then sealed and
174 flushed with 20 mL/min CO₂ for 1 h. After 1 h, CO₂ was reduced to 1 mL/min and vats were
175 continuously purged with 1 mL/min CO₂ for the remainder of the experimental period.
176 Temperature was maintained at 39°C. Fermentor pH and temperature were recorded every 2 min
177 using an automated sensor (Applikon Biotechnology, B.V.).

178 The experiment was operated for 4 consecutive, 10-d periods and re-inoculated with fresh
179 ruminal fluid at the beginning of each period. Each 10-d period consisted of a 7-d adaptation
180 period followed by a 3-d collection period. Effluent was collected in 4-L plastic containers
181 located inside a freezer to maintain an effluent temperature of 4°C and inhibit microbial
182 fermentation. During the adaptation period, effluent was weighed daily, volume recorded, and
183 then contents were discarded. During the collection period, daily effluent collections were mixed
184 in a blender (model 38LL52 Waring, Torrington, CT) for 30 s on the lowest setting and speed
185 controlled further with a PowerStat variable transformer (model 3PN126, Superior Electric,
186 Bristol, CT) set at 35 to create a 1-cm vortex at the top of the blender contents in order to provide
187 adequate mixing without too much abrasive agitation. After mixing, a 100-mL sample was taken
188 and composited over the collection period to determine effluent DM. A 50-mL sample was
189 strained through 8 layers of cheesecloth and a 15-mL subsample was added to 3-mL 25%

190 (vol/vol) *m*-phosphoric acid for determination of VFA [Varian 3300 Gas Chromatograph (FID
191 detector), Varian 4290 Integrator; Rumen Fermentation Profiling Laboratory, West Virginia
192 University, Morgantown, WV; Supelco, 1975, modified to use a 80/120 Carbopack B-DA/4%
193 Carbowax 20M column; Erwin et al., 1961] and NH₃-N (Yang and Varga, 1989). The GC
194 parameters used were 2 m × 2 mm i.d. glass column packed with 80/120 Carbopack B-DA/4%
195 Carbowax 20M (catalog no. 1-1889, Supelco, Inc.), column temperature of 175°C, injector
196 temperature of 200°C, detector temperature of 200°C, N gas used as a carrier at a flow rate of 24
197 mL/min, and an injection volume of 1 µL. An additional 1.00-L sample was composited from
198 each of the 3 collection days, freeze-dried, ground to 1 mm, and stored in a sealed plastic bag at
199 ambient temperature for analyses of DM, OM, NDF, CP, and total purines. In addition to the
200 previously described sampling, on d 10 the contents of each fermentor were processed according
201 to the methods of Griswold et al. (1996), except the initial centrifugation, contents were mixed in
202 the above-described blender for 30 s and strained through 2 layers of 53-µm Nitex fabric
203 (Wildco, Bufflao, NY) into a 2-L plastic container with 5 mL of 50% sulfuric acid added to
204 inhibit microbial growth. Contents were centrifuged 3 times at 20,000 × *g* for 20 min at -4°C and
205 then the pellet was re-suspended in 0.9% saline during the first 2 centrifugations and with 50%
206 methanol during the 3rd centrifugation (Griswold et al., 1996). The final pellet was stored at -4°C
207 until freeze-drying and analyses for DM, OM, and CP [per AOAC (2006) procedures described
208 in Nutrient Analyses section below] and purine (Zinn and Owens, 1986). Purine data were used
209 to calculate bacterial efficiencies using the equations described by Soder et al. (2016).

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211 *Methane Collection and Measurements*

212 Methane measurements were taken every 10 min using a photoacoustic gas monitor
213 (LumaSense Technologies, Inc., Santa Clara, CA) connected to a multiport sampler (CAI, Inc.,
214 Orange, CA) that directed the flow of gas from each fermentor vat. Each cycle (sampling and
215 line flush) required 140 cm³ of the approximately 1.50 L of headspace gas available. Total daily
216 CH₄ production was calculated by determining the difference in CH₄ volume (measured CH₄
217 concentration multiplied by the headspace volume) between each of the 10-min samples and then
218 summing these values for every 24-h period during the collection days. Total daily CH₄
219 production = $\Sigma [\text{CH}_4 \text{ volume}_a - \text{CH}_4 \text{ volume}_b]$, where CH₄ volume_a was CH₄ volume was
220 determined by multiplying the headspace volume by the measured CH₄ concentration and
221 volume_a was taken 10 min after volume_b over each 24-h period during collection days.

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223 *Nutrient Analyses*

224 Samples of orchardgrass, annual ryegrass, canola, rapeseed, and turnip were analyzed by
225 wet chemistry (Dairy One Laboratories, Ithaca, NY) according to the following procedures: DM
226 (method 930.15; AOAC, 2006), CP (method 990.03; AOAC, 2006), RDP (Cornell *Streptomyces*
227 *griseus* enzymatic digestion; Coblenz et al., 1999), fat (method 2003.05; AOAC, 2006) and
228 NDF [Ankom model A200; Mertens (2002) with heat stable α -amylase and sodium sulfite used
229 in the NDF procedures (inclusive of ash)]. Water soluble carbohydrates (WSC) were determined
230 using a Thermo Scientific Genesys 10S Vis Spectrophotometer after incubation in 40°C water
231 both for 1 h, and acid hydrolysis with H₂SO₄ (Smith, 1969). Potassium ferricyanide was used for
232 the colorimetric reaction rather than iodide-potassium oxalate, as potassium ferricyanide proves a
233 more stable reaction for detecting reducing sugars (Miller-Webster et al., 2002). Ethanol-soluble
234 carbohydrates (Hall et al., 1999), starch (Application Note #319; YSI, Inc. Life Sciences, Yellow

235 Springs, OH), minerals (Ca, P, Mg, K, Na, S; Thermo IRIS Advantage HX; CEM Application
236 Note for Acid Digestion, CEM Corp., Matthews, NC), and ether extract (method 2003.045;
237 AOAC, 2006) were also determined. Individual and total GLS concentrations were determined
238 by extracting ground, freeze-dried forage in 70% methanol at 60°C for 15 min. The extracted
239 liquid was filtered through a 0.45 µm syringe filter and analyzed using an ICS-5000+
240 chromatography system (Thermo-Fisher Scientific, Sunnyvale, CA) interfaced to a Q-Exactive
241 orbitrap mass spectrometer (Thermo-Fisher Scientific, Bremen, Germany) equipped with an ultra
242 aqueous polar end-capped analytic column (Restek Corp., Bellefonte, PA).

243 Samples from effluent and microbial pellets were analyzed for DM (method 930.15;
244 AOAC, 2006), OM (method 942.05, AOAC, 2006) and CP (micro-Kjeldahl digestion using 75-
245 mL calibrated tubes with CuSO₄/K₂SO₄ catalyst, method 976.06; AOAC, 2006). Neutral
246 detergent fiber of effluent was determined in the same manner as forage. Concentrations of total
247 purines (Zinn and Owens, 1986) in bacterial isolates and effluent were used to partition effluent
248 N flow into bacterial and nonbacterial fractions and to calculate true digestibilities and flows.
249 Apparent (DM, OM, NDF, and ADF) and true (DM, OM, and CP) nutrient digestibilities were
250 calculated using the following equations (DM as an example):

251 **DM apparently digested** (% of total DM) = [(g of DM fed – g of effluent flow DM) ÷ g of DM
252 fed] × 100, with effluent corrected for g of buffer DM.

253 **DM truly digested** (% of total DM) = {[g of DM fed – (g of effluent flow DM – g of microbial
254 DM)] ÷ g of DM fed} × 100, with effluent corrected for g of buffer DM.

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256 Nitrogenous fraction flows were calculated as follows:

257 **Total N intake** (g/d) = infused urea (g/d) + dietary N (g/d). NH₃-N flow (g/d) = [(effluent NH₃-
258 N in mg/dL × (total effluent flow in mL × 1 dL/100 mL)].

259 **Non-NH₃-N flow** (g/d) = (g of total effluent N flow) – (g of effluent NH₃-N).

260 **Microbial N flow** (g/d) = (g of microbial DM) × (% N in microbes ÷ 100).

261 **Dietary N flow** (g/d) = (g of effluent non-NH₃-N) – (g of effluent microbial N).

262 **Total N flow** (g/d) = (g of effluent NH₃-N flow) + (g of non-NH₃-N flow).

263 **Rumen-degradable N** (mg/d) = (g of total N intake) – (g of dietary N flow).

264

265 Bacterial efficiency was calculated as follows:

266 **Bacterial efficiency** (mg of bacterial N/kg OM truly digested) = (g of effluent bacterial N ÷ g of
267 OM truly digested) × 1,000, where effluent bacterial N (g) = [effluent total N (g/d) × (% bacterial
268 N in effluent total N/100)], and % bacterial N in effluent total n = [effluent purine (mg/g of N) ÷
269 bacterial purine (mg/g of N)] × 100.

270 (Soder et al., 2016)

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272 *Statistical Analysis*

273 Data were analyzed as a 4 × 4 Latin square design using the GLIMMIX procedure of
274 SAS (SAS Institute, Inc., Cary, NC) using fermentor as the experimental unit and fitted to the
275 following model:

$$276 Y_{ijk} = \mu + P_i + F_j + T_k + e_{ijk},$$

277 where Y_{ijk} = the observations for dependent variables, μ = population mean, P_i = mean effect of
278 i th period, F_j = mean effect of j th fermentor, T_k = mean effect of k th diet, and e_{ijk} = residual error.

279 Fermentor, period and error were considered random effects and diet was considered a fixed
280 effect.

281 Temporal analysis of CH₄ concentrations was analyzed using the following model:

$$282 \quad Y_{ijkl} = \mu + P_i + F_j + T_k + E1_{ijk} + H_l + HT_{lk} + E2_{ijkl},$$

283 where Y_{ijk} = the observations for dependent variables, μ = population mean, P_i = mean effect of
284 i th period, F_j = mean effect of j th fermentor, T_k = mean effect of k th diet, $E1_{ijk}$ = whole-plot
285 error, H_l = mean effect of l th hour of day analyzed as repeated measures, HT_{lk} = interaction
286 between l th hour of day and k th diet, and $E2_{ijkl}$ = subplot residual error. Diet was considered a
287 fixed effect and all other parameters were considered to be random. All reported values are least
288 squares means and were compared by least squared minimum difference. Pearson correlation
289 coefficients between dependent variables and forage characteristics were conducted using PROC
290 CORR of SAS. Stepwise linear regression was conducted using PROC REG of SAS to detect
291 predictive statistical associations between forage characteristics and dependent variables.
292 Statistical significant was declared at $P \leq 0.05$, and tendencies at $0.05 < P \leq 0.10$ for all analyses.
293 There were no period or period \times diet interactions; therefore, only main effects are reported.

294

295 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

296

297 *Diet Composition and Nutrient Digestibility*

298 The chemical composition of dietary ingredients and diets are reported in Table 1 and
299 GLS concentration in Table 2. The use of composite sampling for nutrient and GLS analyses
300 precluded the ability for statistical comparison among diets. The orchardgrass used in the current
301 study was of higher quality (greater CP and lower NDF and ADF) than that reported in previous

302 studies (Hafla et al., 2016; Dillard et al., 2017) and is of great nutritive value based on the
303 description of Cherney and Allen (1995; 18- 24% DM, 18 – 25% CP, 40 – 50% NDF, and 1.53 –
304 1.67 Mcal/kg NE_L). The greater quality of the orchardgrass compared with previous studies was
305 likely result of an early harvest date (late April) and differences in fertilization management of
306 the forage used in the current experiment compared with previous studies. Among the brassicas,
307 all quality parameters were similar, while ARG had numerically greater CP and fiber fractions
308 than the brassica forage. All forage used in the current study had numerically higher CP (> 23%)
309 and lower NDF and ADF (16.1 – 29.7% and 10.8 – 21.2%, respectively) compared to typical
310 cool-season perennial forages (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine,
311 2016), and contained 1.61 to 1.98 Mcal/kg NE_L. Furthermore, unlike the majority of forage
312 grasses and legumes, the nutritive quality of brassicas does not decrease significantly as the
313 plants mature (Smith and Collins, 2003). The resulting diets were all of extremely high nutritive
314 value (> 28% CP, < 36% NDF, and < 22% ADF) and of higher quality than the 3-yr average of
315 14 pasture-based dairy farms throughout the northeastern United States (19.5, 51.0, and 31.4%
316 CP, NDF, and ADF, respectively; Hafla et al. 2016). All diets used in the current study were of
317 sufficient quality to meet the CP and energy requirements of a mid-lactation dairy cow (680 kg
318 BW, 45 kg milk/d; NRC, 2001) or a yearling stocker (300 kg BW, 1.35 kg ADG; National
319 Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2016). However, due to their low NDF
320 concentrations, these diets may not have sufficient fiber to optimize nutrient utilization due to
321 rapid passage rate (van Soest, 1994), regardless of sufficient CP and energy.

322 As expected, no GLS were observed in either orchardgrass or annual ryegrass (Table 2).
323 The turnip diet had, numerically, the greatest concentration of GLS of all diets; both CAN and
324 RAP also contained GLS, but in lesser quantities. Among all diets containing GLS,

325 glucobrassicinapin, gluconapin, gluconasturtiin, and progoitrin represented the largest fraction of
326 individual GLS. Sinigrin, glucoerucian, glucoraphanin, and glucoraphenin were also observed in
327 diets, but in lesser amounts. However, sinalbin, glucohlearin, glucoiberin, and glucoibererin
328 were not observed in any of the forage samples. While GLS concentrations vary considerably
329 with species, variety, and growing conditions (Gustine and Jung, 1985), both total and individual
330 GLS present in all brassicas tested were within the range of those reported in the literature (Font
331 et al., 2005; Cartea and Velasco, 2008; Velasco et al., 2008).

332 There were no differences ($P > 0.28$) in apparent DM, OM, and NDF digestibilities or
333 true DM and OM digestibilities among diets (Table 3). Apparent ADF digestibility was greatest
334 ($P \leq 0.04$) in CAN, while no differences ($P > 0.27$) were observed among the other diets. Both
335 Cassida et al. (1994) and Lambert et al. (1987) reported greater apparent DM, OM, and NDF
336 digestibilities for diets containing 40 to 52% brassica and 60 to 48% mixed grass hay. The
337 apparent ADF digestibilities of ARG, RAP, and TUR were similar to that reported by Cassida et
338 al. (1994) and Lambert et al. (1987), but the CAN diet used in the current study was greater than
339 that reported in either study.

340

341 *Fermentor pH, VFA, and CH₄ Production*

342 There were no differences ($P > 0.11$) in mean, minimum, and maximum pH among diets
343 (Table 4). Lower fiber diets tend to have higher rates of digestion and acid production, thereby
344 decreasing ruminal pH (van Soest, 1994); however, lack of differences in pH suggest that fiber
345 differences between the diets were not great enough to exceed the buffering capacity of the
346 system. Keogh et al. (2009) reported that pregnant, non-lactating dairy cows fed 60% forage kale
347 had a mean ruminal pH of 6.32, similar to the mean pH of the brassica diets in the current study.

348 However, ruminal pH of lambs fed 100% forage rapeseed was lower than that of lambs fed
349 100% perennial ryegrass (6.02 and 6.71, respectively; Sun et al., 2015), likely due to less
350 effective fiber in the 100% rapeseed diet.

351 Neither total VFA nor acetate (A) concentrations were different ($P > 0.34$) among diets
352 (Table 4). Propionate (P) was greater ($P \leq 0.05$) in ARG than CAN or RAP, and butyrate (B)
353 was greater ($P = 0.03$) in RAP than ARG. Valerate (V) was greater ($P = 0.011$) in RAP than
354 ARG. Isobutyrate and isovalerate concentrations were greater ($P < 0.01$) in ARG than the
355 brassica diets. All VFA ratios (A:P and A+B:P+V) were greater ($P < 0.01$) in RAP than ARG,
356 with CAN and TUR having median values. The lower A:P ratio observed in ARG was the result
357 of a greater proportion of propionate in ARG at the expense of butyrate. Sun et al. (2012)
358 reported that total VFA concentrations after feeding were greater in rapeseed and turnip than
359 perennial ryegrass (97.0 and 74.2 mol/100 mol, respectively). Keogh et al. (2009) found that the
360 A:P ratio of pregnant, non-lactating dairy cows consuming 60% kale and 40% perennial ryegrass
361 (*Lolium perenne* L.) silage was not different than cows consuming 100% perennial ryegrass
362 silage. However, total VFA concentrations were greater in the 60% kale diet than the 100%
363 perennial ryegrass diet.

364 Methane production (mg/d) was 84% greater ($P < 0.01$) in ARG than the brassica
365 diets, while no difference ($P > 0.28$) was observed among brassicas (Table 4). Furthermore, CH₄
366 per gram of OM fed, per gram of NDF fed, per gram of digestible OM fed, and per gram of
367 digestible NDF fed also followed a similar pattern with no differences ($P > 0.18$) observed
368 among brassicas, but all brassicas being lower ($P < 0.01$) than ARG. A significant ($P < 0.01$) diet
369 × hour of day interaction was observed, such that a diurnal pattern in CH₄ production was
370 observed in ARG (Figure 1). However, there was no difference ($P > 0.05$) in hourly CH₄

371 production throughout the day. This response was due to CH₄ production of each of the brassica
372 diets being at least 6 times lower than the ARG diet resulting in a SEM (0.51 mg CH₄/h) that was
373 similar to the hourly mean of the brassica diets. Sun et al. (2012) reported that gram of CH₄ per
374 kilogram of DMI was 25% lower in lambs fed forage rapeseed than perennial ryegrass. However,
375 the authors reported no differences in gram of CH₄ per kilogram of DMI between perennial
376 ryegrass and turnip, disagreeing with the current study. These differences are due to the reduced
377 DMI observed in the lambs fed turnip compared to those fed perennial ryegrass, while DMI was
378 similar for lambs consuming rapeseed and perennial ryegrass (Sun et al., 2012). In a separate
379 study, Sun et al. (2015) reported a 22% reduction in CH₄ production in lambs fed forage
380 rapeseed compared with perennial ryegrass for 15 weeks. Brask et al. (2013b) reported that
381 lactating dairy cattle consuming TMR diets with and without different rapeseed by-products (i.e.,
382 rapeseed cake, whole cracked rapeseed, and rapeseed oil) included had similar daily milk
383 production (28.3 kg/d), milk fat content (39.7 g/kg), and milk protein concentration (33.0 g/kg);
384 while CH₄ emissions were lower in the rapeseed supplemented cattle (17.5 vs. 20.4 L/kg of
385 energy corrected milk and 5.44 vs. 6.32 % of gross energy intake, respectively). Storlien et al.
386 (2017) reported that inclusion of a rapeseed concentrate in TMR-supplemented, pasture-based,
387 lactating dairy cattle increased milk production (31.7 vs. 29.6 kg/d, with and without rapeseed,
388 respectively), but no difference was observed in energy corrected milk (26.6 kg/d). Furthermore,
389 milk fat and protein were lower in cattle consuming the rapeseed supplement (30.4 vs. 34.8 g/kg
390 and 29.8 vs. 30.3 g/kg, respectively). Enteric CH₄ measured was lower in rapeseed supplemented
391 cattle, regardless of measurement method (221 vs. 251 g/day, 8.1 vs. 9.0 g/kg of energy
392 corrected milk, and 27.4 vs. 33.6 g/kg of concentrate fed, respectively). Methane reduction in

393 the current study was greater than that reported in previous studies; however, this could be
394 attributed to inherent differences between *in vivo* and *in vitro* studies (Hristov et al., 2012).

395 In the current study, differences in CH₄ production did not follow typical patterns for
396 VFA ratios. This was also observed by Sun et al. (2012) who reported no correlation between
397 CH₄ yield as g CH₄/kg DMI and total and individual VFA. This suggests that GLS directly affect
398 methanogens or protozoa populations, but do not alter gram-positive bacteria populations.
399 Ohene-Adjei et al. (2008) indicated that phylogenetic analysis of ruminal fluid from sheep fed a
400 barley-based diet and supplemented with garlic oil (contains organosulphur compounds similar
401 to GLS) inhibited *Methanobrevibacter ruminantium* when compared to non-supplemented sheep.
402 Furthermore, Patra et al. (2010) reported no significant changes in protozoal populations in sheep
403 supplemented with garlic oil compared to non-supplemented sheep. The authors then concluded
404 that organosulphur compounds inhibited methanogenic archaea without affecting other
405 microorganisms found in the rumen. Busquet et al. (2005) proposed that reduction in
406 methanogens was due to inhibition of 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme A (HMG-CoA)
407 reductase, thus affecting the unique membrane lipids that contain ether linked glycerols and
408 long-chain isoprenoid alcohols, which are not present in other microorganisms found in the
409 rumen (De Rosa et al., 1986).

410 Correlation analyses between daily CH₄ production and the individual GLS that were
411 present in the diets revealed a significant ($P < 0.045$) negative relationship between daily CH₄
412 production and glucobrassicinapin, sinigrin, glucobrassicin, gluconapin, glucoraphanin,
413 glucoraphenin, progoitrin, and total GLS concentration (Table 5). Gluconasturtiin tended ($P =$
414 0.076) to be negatively correlated; however, glucoerucin was not significantly correlated ($P =$
415 0.207) with daily CH₄ production. Step-wise multiple regression analysis between CH₄

416 production and nutritive quality parameters, total GLS, and individual GLS concentration
417 showed that NDF explained 75% of the variation in daily CH₄ production and CH₄ production
418 per OM fed, 73% of the variation in CH₄ per digestible OM fed, and 85% of the variation in CH₄
419 per digestible NDF fed (Table 6). Furthermore, when methane was expressed per gram of NDF
420 fed, NFC was the only independent variable to enter the model and explained 73% of the
421 variation in CH₄ production. Therefore, even though a significant negative correlation was
422 observed between CH₄ production and total GLS concentration, NDF still plays the most
423 important role in determining CH₄ production from forage-based diets. Previous studies (Brask
424 et al., 2013b; Storlien et al., 2017) showed that addition of rapeseed cake to dairy cows on
425 pasture or consuming a TMR also significantly reduced CH₄ per kg of concentrate and CH₄ as %
426 of GE intake, respectively. These studies were able to more closely control NDF and fat
427 concentrations of the diets, allowing the researchers to remove these confounding factors. In
428 order to better determine the direct effect of GLS on CH₄ production when grazing forage
429 brassicas on pasture, diets will need to be balanced for fiber and NFC components to prevent the
430 effects of NDF masking any possible effects of GLS on CH₄ production.

431

432 *Nitrogen Metabolism*

433 While DM intake was kept constant, due to differences in CP concentration of diets,
434 dietary N was greatest ($P < 0.01$) in CAN and TUR and least ($P < 0.01$) in RAP (Table 7). Luo et
435 al. (2015) found that DMI of lambs consuming fresh forage rapeseed tended to be greater than
436 lambs fed perennial (0.895 vs 0.826 kg/d, respectively). Furthermore, N concentration of
437 rapeseed was 8% greater than the perennial ryegrass; this led to a 23% higher daily N intake in
438 lambs fed rapeseed compared to perennial ryegrass. Effluent NH₃-N concentration was 26%

439 greater in ARG than the brassica diets and the same pattern was observed in NH₃-N flows. Kaur
440 et al. (2010) found that daily ruminal NH₃-N concentrations were not different in lambs
441 consuming 10, 25, or 40% forage rapeseed with a corn silage-based TMR (22.6 ± 1.4 mg/dL).
442 Furthermore, the authors reported no differences in N intake among diets. In the current study,
443 true CP digestibility was 25% greater ($P < 0.01$) in ARG and CAN than RAP and TUR. Sun et
444 al. (2012) reported that the apparent CP digestibility of forage rapeseed and turnip in lambs was
445 greater than perennial ryegrass (30 and 17%, respectively). Furthermore, Cassida et al. (1994)
446 reported that apparent CP digestibility increased linearly with increasing amounts of tyfon (*B.*
447 *campestris* var *rapa* L. × *B. pekinensis* [Lour.] Rupr.) in lambs fed a diet of mixed-grass hay
448 and tyfon. Total N flow was greater ($P = 0.04$) in ARG than CAN in the current study, while
449 RAP and TUR had intermediate values. However, no difference ($P > 0.43$) was observed in
450 NAN flows among all diets.

451 Bacterial N flows were 47% greater ($P \leq 0.01$) in ARG and CAN than RAP and TUR,
452 while dietary N flows were 75% greater ($P < 0.01$) in RAP and TUR than ARG and CAN (Table
453 7). Furthermore, bacterial efficiency, measured as g N/kg of truly digestible DM and OM, was
454 greater ($P \leq 0.01$) in ARG and CAN than RAP and TUR. Busquet et al. (2005) found no
455 differences in dietary N flow, bacterial N flow, or bacterial efficiency per OM truly digested in a
456 continuous culture system fed a 50:50 forage:concentrate diet and supplemented with or without
457 garlic oil. In the current study, the greater bacterial efficiency observed in CAN compared to
458 RAP and TUR could be a result of the greater apparent ADF digestibility of CAN.

459

460

CONCLUSIONS

461 When mixed with orchardgrass, forage brassicas can provide a suitable alternative to
462 cool-season annual grass pastures such as ARG during times when productivity of cool-season
463 grasses is low (i.e., late fall and summer forage slump). In addition to being high in nutritive
464 quality, all three brassica diets (CAN, RAP, and TUR) also significantly lowered CH₄ production
465 compared to ARG. Furthermore, CAN provided greater ruminal bacterial efficiency than the
466 other brassicas, making it the superior variety in this study. While other studies (Brask et al.,
467 2013b; Storlien et al., 2017) have established a link between organosulphur secondary plant
468 metabolites and CH₄ reduction, in the current study we were unable to establish a causal
469 relationship between individual or total GLS and CH₄ production even though a significant CH₄
470 reduction occurred. Use of brassicas in a ruminant grazing system could extend the fall grazing
471 season and reduce winter feed costs while increasing animal efficiency and decreasing
472 greenhouse gas emissions. However, more research is needed on the long-term effects of grazing
473 brassicas to determine if these effects can be observed in pasture-based ruminants.

474

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622 **Table 1.** Chemical composition (% of DM) of individual forages and diets fed during continuous
 623 culture fermentation

Item	Ingredient					Diet ¹			
	Annual Ryegrass	Canola	Rapeseed	Turnip	Orchard- grass	ARG	CAN	RAP	TUR
OM	88.1	89.3	88.6	85.8	90.2	89.2	89.7	89.4	88.0
CP	30.2	28.2	23.2	22.2	34.0	32.1	31.1	28.6	28.1
RDP, % of CP	83	87	89	87	80	82	84	85	84
NDF	29.7	16.1	16.6	17.2	41.2	35.5	28.7	28.9	29.2
ADF	21.2	10.8	11.8	12.0	22.8	21.2	16.8	17.3	17.4
Lignin	5.3	0.8	1.3	1.3	2.5	3.9	1.7	1.9	1.9
NFC ²	21.9	39.2	44.3	42.1	10.5	16.2	24.9	27.4	26.3
WSC ³	21.6	31.4	34.1	33.2	11.9	16.8	21.7	23.0	22.6
ESC ⁴	19.6	24.7	24.6	26.9	7.9	13.8	16.3	16.3	17.4
Starch	0.2	0.5	1.7	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.4	1.0	0.3
Ether extract	6.2	5.7	4.5	4.3	4.5	5.4	5.1	4.5	4.4
NE _M ⁵ , Mcal/kg	1.63	1.96	1.83	1.74	1.61	1.62	1.79	1.72	1.68
NE _G ⁵ , Mcal/kg	1.03	1.30	1.21	1.12	0.99	1.01	1.15	1.10	1.06
NE _L ⁵ , Mcal/kg	1.68	1.98	1.87	1.79	1.61	1.65	1.81	1.74	1.70
Ca	0.64	1.78	1.98	2.47	0.42	0.53	1.10	1.20	1.45
P	0.28	0.40	0.36	0.35	0.43	0.36	0.42	0.40	0.39
Mg	0.18	0.25	0.22	0.24	0.28	0.23	0.42	0.25	0.26
K	3.62	2.63	2.64	3.44	3.03	3.33	2.83	2.84	3.24
Na	0.04	0.08	0.10	0.06	0.19	0.11	0.13	0.14	0.12
S	0.40	0.72	0.73	0.88	0.43	0.42	0.58	0.58	0.66
Cu, ppm	7	4	4	5	9	8	7	7	7

624 ¹Diets calculated using actual nutrient composition and proportion of individual forages (DM
 625 basis); ARG = 50% orchardgrass + 50% annual ryegrass; CAN = 50% orchardgrass + 50%
 626 canola; RAP = 50% orchardgrass + 50% rapeseed; TUR = 50% orchardgrass + 50% turnip.

627 ²Calculated as NFC = 100 – (CP% + NDF% + ether extract% + ash%).

628 ³WSC = water-soluble carbohydrate.

629 ⁴ESC = ethanol-soluble carbohydrate.

630 ⁵Estimated by the NRC (2001) model.

631

632 **Table 2.** Total and individual glucosinolate concentrations (mg/g DM) of individual forages and diets fed during continuous culture
 633 fermentation

Glucosinolate ²	Ingredient					Diet ¹			
	Annual Ryegrass	Canola	Rapeseed	Turnip	Orchard- grass	ARG	CAN	RAP	TUR
Glucobrassicinapin	0.00	5.72	5.13	17.29	0.00	0.00	2.86	2.57	8.65
Progoitrin	0.00	3.04	9.66	15.26	0.00	0.00	1.52	4.83	7.63
Gluconapin	0.00	1.00	1.42	4.15	0.00	0.00	0.50	0.71	2.08
Glucobrassicin	0.00	0.95	1.25	1.96	0.00	0.00	0.48	0.63	0.98
Gluconasturtiin	0.00	0.68	1.16	3.95	0.00	0.00	0.34	0.58	1.98
Glucoraphanin	0.00	0.16	0.63	0.42	0.00	0.00	0.08	0.32	0.21
Glucoerucin	0.00	0.01	0.05	0.41	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.03	0.21
Sinigrin	0.00	0.08	0.23	0.31	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.12	0.16
Glucoraphenin	0.00	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.03
Total	0.00	11.68	19.51	43.80	0.00	0.00	5.84	9.76	21.90

634 ¹Diets calculated using actual nutrient composition and proportion of individual forages (DM basis); ARG = 50% orchardgrass + 50%
 635 annual ryegrass; CAN = 50% orchardgrass + 50% canola; RAP = 50% orchardgrass + 50% rapeseed; TUR = 50% orchardgrass + 50%
 636 turnip.

637 ²No detectable levels of gluoiberin, glucoiberin, gluochlearin, or sinalbin were found in any of the forages or diets tested.

638 **Table 3.** Nutrient digestibility of annual ryegrass, canola, rapeseed, and turnip fed with
 639 orchardgrass during continuous culture fermentation
 640

Item	Diet ¹				SEM
	ARG	CAN	RAP	TUR	
Apparent Digestibility					
DM, %	44.5	44.7	45.3	46.0	2.77
OM, %	61.6	62.5	63.6	65.0	2.84
NDF, %	38.1	52.8	40.9	44.5	5.57
ADF, %	52.1 ^a	64.0 ^b	48.8 ^a	53.9 ^a	3.15
True Digestibility					
DM, %	70.0	66.4	69.5	62.4	2.86
OM, %	89.7	86.4	90.1	82.6	3.13

641 ¹ARG = 50% orchardgrass + 50% annual ryegrass; CAN = 50% orchardgrass + 50% canola;
 642 RAP = 50% orchardgrass + 50% rapeseed; TUR = 50% orchardgrass + 50% turnip.

643 ^{a-b}Within a row, means without a common superscript differ ($P \leq 0.05$).

644 **Table 4.** Fermentor pH, VFA concentration and molar proportion, and CH₄ output of annual
 645 ryegrass, canola, rapeseed, and turnip fed with orchardgrass during continuous culture
 646 fermentation

Item	Diet ¹				SEM
	ARG	CAN	RAP	TUR	
pH					
Mean	6.61	6.29	6.41	6.57	0.142
Minimum	6.40 ^a	6.08 ^b	6.14 ^{a,b}	6.16 ^{a,b}	0.078
Maximum	6.95	6.73	7.04	6.69	0.201
Total VFA, mM	90.2	84.8	88.9	84.9	4.68
Individual VFA, mol/100 mol					
Acetate (A)	48.10	42.30	45.14	42.72	2.353
Propionate (P)	25.82 ^a	22.28 ^b	21.80 ^b	23.66 ^{a,b}	1.092
Butyrate (B)	11.44 ^a	15.53 ^{a,b}	16.80 ^b	14.21 ^{a,b}	1.478
Isobutyrate	0.84 ^a	0.39 ^b	0.42 ^b	0.43 ^b	0.044
Valerate (V)	3.22 ^a	3.98 ^{a,b}	4.37 ^b	3.55 ^{a,b}	0.256
Isovalerate	0.74 ^a	0.30 ^b	0.33 ^b	0.32 ^b	0.047
A:P	1.86 ^a	1.90 ^a	2.08 ^b	1.80 ^a	0.049
A+B:P+V	2.05 ^a	2.20 ^{a,b}	2.36 ^b	2.09 ^a	0.057
CH ₄					
mg CH ₄ /d	68.9 ^a	13.1 ^b	7.4 ^b	13.1 ^b	5.77
mg of CH ₄ /g of OM fed	0.94 ^a	0.18 ^b	0.18 ^b	0.10 ^b	0.079
mg of CH ₄ /g of NDF fed	2.37 ^a	0.56 ^b	0.31 ^b	0.55 ^b	0.204
mg of CH ₄ /g of digestible OM fed	2.22 ^a	0.30 ^b	0.22 ^b	0.37 ^b	0.139
mg of CH ₄ /g of digestible NDF fed	1.37 ^a	0.25 ^b	0.14 ^b	0.24 ^b	0.119

647 ¹ARG = 50% orchardgrass + 50% annual ryegrass; CAN = 50% orchardgrass + 50% canola;
 648 RAP = 50% orchardgrass + 50% rapeseed; TUR = 50% orchardgrass + 50% turnip.
 649 ^{a-c}Within a row, means without a common superscript differ ($P \leq 0.05$).

650 **Table 5.** Correlation coefficients (r) between individual and total glucosinolate concentrations
 651 (mg/g DM) and daily CH₄ production (mg/d) of fermentors fed annual ryegrass, canola,
 652 rapeseed, or turnip with orchardgrass

Glucosinolate ¹	r	P-value
Glucobrassicinapin	-0.523	0.038
Sinigrin	-0.643	0.007
Glucobrassicin	-0.732	0.001
Glucoerucin	-0.333	0.207
Gluconapin	-0.509	0.044
Gluconasturtiin	-0.456	0.076
Glucoraphanin	-0.670	0.005
Glucoraphenin	-0.787	< 0.001
Progoitrin	-0.593	0.015
Total	-0.567	0.022

653 ¹No correlation was tested between daily CH₄ production and sinalbin, glucohearin, glucoiberin,
 654 or glucoiberin due to lack of measurable concentrations in any forage analyzed.

655 **Table 6.** Multiple regression of nutritive quality parameters and glucosinolate concentrations on
 656 daily CH₄ production, CH₄ production per OM fed, CH₄ production per NDF fed, CH₄
 657 production per digestible OM fed, and CH₄ production per digestible NDF fed of fermentors fed
 658 annual ryegrass, canola, rapeseed, and turnip with orchardgrass

	Independent Variable	Partial r ²	P-value
Daily CH ₄ production, mg/d	NDF	0.75	< 0.0001
CH ₄ production per OM fed, mg/g	NDF	0.75	< 0.0001
CH ₄ production per NDF fed, mg/g	NFC	0.73	< 0.0001
CH ₄ production per digestible OM fed, mg/g	NDF	0.73	< 0.0001
CH ₄ production per digestible NDF fed, mg/g	NDF	0.85	< 0.0001

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661 **Table 7.** Nitrogen metabolism of annual ryegrass, canola, rapeseed, and turnip fed with
 662 orchardgrass during continuous culture fermentation

Item	Diet ¹				SEM
	ARG	CAN	RAP	TUR	
N intake, g/d ²	4.33 ^b	4.83 ^a	4.27 ^c	4.83 ^a	0.004
NH ₃ -N, mg/dL	28.4 ^a	21.1 ^b	22.2 ^b	20.1 ^b	0.91
True CP digestibility, %	94.3 ^a	91.0 ^a	69.6 ^b	70.4 ^b	2.84
N flows, g/d					
Total N	2.95 ^a	2.67 ^b	2.70 ^{ab}	2.70 ^{ab}	0.100
NH ₃ -N	1.14 ^a	0.85 ^b	0.90 ^b	0.80 ^b	0.038
NAN	1.80	1.83	1.80	1.90	0.092
Bacterial N	1.60 ^a	1.46 ^a	0.73 ^b	0.89 ^b	0.159
Dietary N	0.20 ^a	0.37 ^a	1.07 ^b	1.21 ^b	0.115
Bacterial efficiency					
g N/kg DM truly digested	29.9 ^a	27.5 ^a	16.6 ^b	15.4 ^b	2.63
g N/kg OM truly digested	27.5 ^a	24.7 ^a	14.4 ^b	13.2 ^b	2.40

663 ¹ARG = 50% orchardgrass + 50% annual ryegrass; CAN = 50% orchardgrass + 50% canola;
 664 RAP = 50% orchardgrass + 50% rapeseed; TUR = 50% orchardgrass + 50% turnip.

665 ²N intake (g/d) = dietary N (g/d) + urea-N from buffer (g/d).

666 ^{a-b}Within a row, means without a common superscript differ ($P \leq 0.05$).

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668

Figure Captions

669 **Figure 1.** Temporal CH₄ production of orchardgrass fed with annual ryegrass (ARG), canola
670 (CAN), rapeseed (RAP), and turnip (TUR) during continuous culture fermentation. Error bars
671 indicate standard errors. Vertical arrows indicate times of feeding.
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